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FORMATION OF PLAY SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *In this article, the physical healthy development of children in the preschool education system today, especially in the era of globalization, inviting children to active physical life, leading a healthy lifestyle, young It is focused on increasing the physical education, physical fitness and physical qualities of the generation, increasing the opportunities of children to play outdoor physical exercises and action games rather than electronic games.*

Keywords: *children of preschool age, game, skills, action games, physical qualities, education.*

INTRODUCTION

In the world, many researches devoted to the tasks of raising preschool children are studying the problems of introducing innovative technologies for increasing movement activity, developing their physical qualities, and developing age-appropriate types of control and standards. The main issues of scientific research work are periodically improved, and various new aspects are discovered in the field. Developing the preschool education system, increasing the physical activity of children from birth to school age, creating new methods for solving the problems of developing their physical qualities, developing modern pedagogical systems for physical education in preschool and primary educational organizations, there is a need to develop methods and tasks for solving important issues, such as establishing early learning systems that ensure early education of young parents in the family.

P.S. Lesgaft considers games as one of the most effective means of physical education and upbringing. He allocated a large part of the lessons of social education to games: for games for small classes he allocated half of the lesson, for middle classes - a third of the lesson. According to him, action games have an important educational and educational value, and they involve more complex movements than individual gymnastic exercises. He tried to introduce active games into schools and kindergartens as the most important means of physical and spiritual education.

The importance of action games is that they are understandable and easy for children of different ages. Although there are many types of action games related to ethnic and other characteristics, they

reflect the general descriptive aspects related to that particular activity, such as the interaction of the participants with the environment and the perception of real life. In order to achieve a set goal in connection with sudden and ever-changing conditions and a wide range of actions, goal-oriented and goal-oriented actions require the manifestation of creative qualities, activity and initiative. Such a wide use of opportunities reflecting independent and relatively free actions, which are combined with the fulfillment of conditions accepted or set according to one's own will, with the subordination of personal interest to the general, is connected with the vivid manifestation of emotions. All this, from a methodological point of view, action games are described as a pedagogical tool for the multifaceted, complex effect of education. Complexity is expressed in the formation of movement skills, development and improvement of vitally important physical, mental and moral-will qualities. In order to have such an all-round effect, it is recommended to take into account the physical capabilities of the children and the size of the loads, as well as the direction chosen in the use of games.

Therefore, children's outdoor games and recreational activities have health, educational and educational value, and are considered very convenient for physical training. They improve the physical development of children, have a positive effect on the nervous system, and strengthen health. Due to the fact that this is a very exciting sports activity that creates a great physical load for the child, it is necessary to take these loads into account when organizing training and games [53; p. 89].

Almost every game has running, jumping, throwing, balance exercises, etc. In the games, all the basic physical qualities of the child, such as strength, quickness, are cultivated and various movement skills and abilities are improved.

Kindergarten children develop and improve various skills in basic movements (running, jumping, throwing, crawling, etc.) during play. The rapid change of situations during the game teaches the child to use actions known to him in accordance with this or that situation. All this has a positive effect on improving motor skills.

The game is the first activity, the main role of which belongs to the formation of the personality. In games, children reflect accumulated experiences, deepen and strengthen their ideas about the depicted events and life. A child understands the world in the process of activity like adults. Engaging in games enriches participants with new emotions, imagination and understanding. Games expand the scope of imagination, develop quick understanding and analysis of observation, teach to compare and generalize what they see and to draw conclusions from the environmental phenomena observed by them. In action games, the qualities of correct assessment of environment and time ratios, quick and correct attention to situations that occur with frequent changes in the game are developed. Organizing and conducting mobile games in summer and winter conditions and seasonal changes requires the pedagogue to carefully guide the process.

Action games are also very important in training physical qualities: quickness, agility, strength, flexibility. Games also educate children in solidarity, solidarity and responsibility. The rule of the game educates the skill of conscious discipline, honesty, self-control, ability to "catch oneself" after strong influences, to control one's individuality. Therefore, it is appropriate to have a positive approach to physical education of children and, in necessary cases, to independently create game tasks that include the types of movements that the child needs especially at this time.

In action games and other games, a wide area should be chosen so that children can play freely without being cramped in the environment. The duration of various games is different: this is important when choosing them, because the excessive duration of the game causes symptoms of exhaustion in children, which should not be allowed, otherwise the benefit from the game will turn into a loss. It is inevitable to leave. When determining the game, it is necessary to maximize the neuromuscular strength that each child can develop without signs of fatigue.

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